

H2020 Work Programme

D5.5 - Project videos- First version

Lead Contractor: FVA

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This document is the BIOBEC project videos – First version (contract no. 101023381) corresponding to D5.5 (M9) led by FVA. This document describes the project First video produced by the BIObec project, whose main objective is to ensure motivated co-creation, stakeholder involvement, dissemination and communication

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023381. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Project details			
Project acronym	BIObec	Start / Duration	01/09/2021 – 30 months
Topic	BBI-2020-SO4-S3 -Create and interlink bio-based education centres to meet industry's needs of skills and competences	Call identifier	H2020-BBI-JTI-2020
Type of Action	CSA	Coordinator	Davide Viaggi (UNIBO)
Contact persons	Louis Ferrini		
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Deliverable details			
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Title	Project videos- First version		
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Deliverable responsible	FVA	Contact person	Louis Ferrini

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Acronyms and abbreviations

DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DOA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
GP	General Public
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PM	Policy Makers
SC	Scientific Community
SI	Software industry
TM	Trade Media
WP	Work Package

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1.Executive summary

Two professional videos within the project are foreseen in Task 5.2 Online & Offline Dissemination & Communication activities.

This deliverable provides a brief description of the design and development of the first of two project videos due in M9.

2.First project video

The first video was design and developed by partner FVA with the contribution mainly of SIE and from all other partners.

 [Link to the video](#)

2.1. Video's aim

The main messages to promote with this first video were to present:

- the project concept
- its objectives
- the overall expected impact

2.2. Video contents

The first contents have been elaborated by FVA and shared with all partners to receive feedbacks and additional contents.

Following is the script of the video and the storyboard used by the video editors and graphic designers.

SCRIPT

The European shift to a bio-based economy will create new jobs and stimulate growth in an emerging economy sector. Therefore, unlocking the full potential of the bioeconomy and its value chains will require new skills and new competencies.

There is a demand for education to deliver qualified workforce for this emerging sector.

BIObec is a project that has the objective of bridging the education system with the bio-based industry by linking universities, innovation labs, and research and development centres with industrial actors and regions.

BIObec will boost the contribution of the education sector for the development of the bioeconomy by designing Bio-Based Education Centres to meet industry needs.

The project proposes a holistic framework for multi-level BioBased Education Centres, that merges the traditional idea of education centres, with the concept of knowledge hubs.

BIObec will design six BioBased Education Centres pilots with a wide geographical coverage to address a range of topics on various value chains and to be geared at academia, primary producers and businesses ranging from SMEs to large companies. They will provide tailored educational framework according to the needs of different EU regions, embedding flexibility and modularity responding to European complexity.

The project mobilises a Consortium of 19 partners, from 12 different European Countries, key players in Bioeconomy Education from different perspectives, ranging from academia to industry.

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The partners will work in conjunction with a wide network of European Implementation and Replication Working Groups and stakeholders for the wide deployment of the BBEC model
To achieve these outcomes BIObec will:

- Provide an overview of regional requirements and define criteria and conditions for the Bio-Based Education Centres;
- Define the most effective design and business models for the development of those Bio-Based Education Centres and their activities;
- Provide governance plans, learning programs and feasibility assessments
- Develop a strategy for rolling out and replicating the Bio-Based Education Centres at European and International level;
- Involve stakeholders to co-create, disseminate and communicate Bioeconomy-related concepts among society

Collaborate with previous and ongoing EU funded projects to maximize the impact of their results

STORYBOARD

Contents (speaking voice)	Key words/key phrases + graphics
<p>Europe's shift to a bioeconomy will create new jobs and stimulate growth in an emerging economy sector. Therefore, unlocking the full potential of the bioeconomy and its value chains will require new skills and new competencies.</p> <p>There is a demand for education to deliver qualified workforce for this emerging sector</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlock the full potential of the bioeconomy • new skills and new competencies. <p>+ graphics displaying the world+nature (as ref. to bioeconomy)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demand for education of qualified workforce
<p>BIObec is a BBI JU funded project aiming at bridging the education system with the bio-based industry by linking universities, innovation labs, and R&D centres with industrial actors and regions</p> <p>BIObec will boost the contribution of the education sector for the development of the bioeconomy by designing Bio-Based Education Centres to meet industry needs.</p> <p>The project proposes a holistic framework for multi-level Biobased Education Centres, BBEC, that merges the traditional idea of education centres, with the concept of knowledge hubs.</p> <p>BIObec will design six BBEC pilots with a wide geographical coverage to address a range of topics on various value chains and to be geared at academia, primary producers and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • bio-based industry • education system • + graphics displaying the different actors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the contribution of the education sector • Bio-Based Education Centres • meet industry needs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How? <p>+ graphics</p>

businesses ranging from SMEs to large companies. The BBECs concept will provide tailored educational framework according to the needs of different EU regions, embedding flexibility and modularity responding to European complexity.	
Project strategy:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • six pilot centres
The project mobilises a network of 19 partners, from 12 different European Countries key players in the Bioeconomy Education from different perspectives, ranging from academia to industry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 19 partners from 12 European Countries + Partners logos
The partners will work in conjunction with a wide network of European Implementation and Replication Working Groups and stakeholders for the wide deployment of the BBEC model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation and Replication Working Groups (IRWG) • Multistakeholders network to implement and replicate the BBECs
To achieve these outcomes BIObec will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a comprehensive overview of regional requirements for the Bio-Based Education Centres; • Define the most effective design and business models for developing and establishing a BBEC and its activities; • Provide governance plans, learning programs and feasibility assessments for the proposed BBECs; • Develop a strategy for rolling out and replicating the BBECs at European and international level; • Motivate stakeholders to co-create, disseminate and communicate for the benefits of the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impacts • Goals • Overview of requisite needs • Definition of criteria and conditions for the BBECs • Design of business models for the BBECs implementation • Provide governance and learning programs for the BBECs • Develop a strategy for the BBECs replication • Stimulate co-creation, dissemination and communication activities among stakeholders
Contacts: To be updated about BIObec project activities and opportunities follow us on our social media channels and subscribe to the BIObec newsletter.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to website, mail and social Website: https://biobec.eu/ General info: info@biobec.eu TWT: https://twitter.com/BIObec_eu LinkedIN: https://www.linkedin.com/company/biobec/

Table 1. Video storyboard table

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2.3. Video's visual aspect

Considering the contents of this first video that deals with educational topics and the promotion of the project, two alternatives for the visual look and feel were taken into account: cartoonish or real videos style. We preferred to use real impact videos to transfer the importance of the bio-based education to the general public and the relevant stakeholders.

Modern transitions for the videos and the text were used to give a more attractive aspect to the final product.

Image 1 : Some screenshots of the video

2.4. Video's soundtrack and speech

The soundtrack used was selected from a freeware website upbeat.io and the voice over the video was generated from a professional AI text to speech online website play.ht